

LANGUAGE POLICY AS A BRANCH OF APPLIED LINGUISTICS.

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Annotation In linguistic literature, the relationship between language and society, social differentiation of language, linguistic situation in society, language sociality, language and social relations, the influence of social factors on language, bilingualism and multilingualism, language policy, nation and national language problems are considered important tasks of sociolinguistics.

Key words Linguistic literature, language and society, social factors, language policy, sociolinguistics, bilingualism and multilingualism.

In this respect, the social differentiation of the language comes from the fact that it is composed of members of the society with different professions, different professions, different mental and spiritual capabilities, and accordingly, each social group has an active and inactive vocabulary. The territorial affiliation of the members of the society is also different, of course. Therefore, social and regional dialects are ways of language use of social groups according to their profession, profession, mental and spiritual ability and territorial origin.

It is not a secret to any of the specialists of this discipline today that there is little work to be done only within the framework of linguistics for the complete study of the language. Therefore, the achievements of other disciplines are widely used in modern linguistic research.

As a result of such efforts, fields such as linguistics, cognitive linguistics, ethnolinguistics, psycholinguistics, ethnopsycholinguistics, and pragmalinguistics are developing, and these fields are gaining importance because they approach language as a phenomenon in constant movement, growth and change, unlike

traditional structuralism. Sociolinguistics, as a field that emerged at the intersection of sociology and linguistics, looks for the foundations of language from society, the foundations of society from language, investigates the influence of socio-political factors on language and other issues.

According to Kaplan and Joseph Lo Bianco Language Policy is a branch of applied linguistics. Language Policy is also known as language planning and has a relationship with other fields as language education, language revitalization and language ideology. Linguistics plays an important role in the development of language teaching theory. Additionally, the theory of language teaching states answers to questions about the nature of language. Teachers are provided with a formal knowledge of language system and the nature of language by applied linguistics. This helps teachers to understand the nature of language learning. This leads teachers to make their decisions on appropriate approach and teaching techniques.

The article “Growing your own onion” by Dr. DJ Kaiser (2018) gives a clear understanding for ESL/EFL teachers how to write their own Language Planning and Policy Proposals. It assists teachers to improve language instruction and to increase teacher agency. According to Dr. DJ Kaiser writing Language Planning and Policy Proposal is similar to Growing an Onion, as both of these things require long step by step procedure. It means that every teacher should develop and create his or her own proposal with conscious effort considering English learners’ need and interest. Moreover, they should investigate various activities, modify them and make suitable for learners.

There is no doubt that, Language variation exists in all languages. They are different from each other systematically and even within a single language there are various ways of expressing the same meaning. If we speak about the linguistic structure of languages they may differ from each other at the morphological, phonetic, syntactic, phonological and lexical levels. Besides this, there exist other

essential factors as regional, geographic and social factors that can highly influence to language variation.

For instance, in Andijan region the Language Variation is highly noticeable in using different dialects in different parts of the region. In Izboskan region people say “bicha” instead of “opa”, in Xojaobod “opobi” or “egachi” that means “sister” in English, “bo’la” instead of “jiyan” that means “nephew”, “ogap chiq” instead of “olib chiq” that means “bring”.

The outcome of language contact is language convergence that occurs in the result of extensive, long-term contact situation. Convergence happens when two different languages become more similar due to contact between them. For instance, Kirghizistan, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Tajikistan and Uzbekistan have some features of linguistic convergence as a result, of a long-standing linguistic contact between nations.

Speaking about the influence of language and society it is necessary to explain how language affects society. As experts have rightly pointed out, the impact of language on society has been little studied compared to the impact of society on language, and there is even skepticism about such an impact. In our opinion, it is doubtful that the tool, which is a tool of thinking, does not influence the society, because the language constantly moves the society, and the most primitive reflection of this kind of influence can be seen in its task of forming and transmitting information. The influence of society on the language is visible in tangible linguistic results, therefore, this kind of influence does not raise doubts, the results of influence can be seen at a glance. The results of the influence of language on society are not expressed in language materials that a linguist can record, but in social life itself. The lack of evidence through specific linguistic material led to the non-discovery of the mechanisms of language influence on society. For example, the influence of the literary language on society can be seen, first of all, in ensuring national unity, and in addition, in the formation and improvement of public literacy, in the development of science and culture, and in education. Counting can be continued again. In

general, as long as information is transmitted in society, it is impossible not to participate in it and not have an influence of language.

So, there is a constant interaction between language and society. Development of science and education, culture and art, technology and statehood are the main factors influencing language and society. The driving force of this influence process is, of course, a person and the society to which he belongs. The needs of the society cause the language to expand within the scope of the task, to be filled with style.

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